

On the Potential for Elastic Tailoring in Layered Composites- Buckling Considerations

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Keywords: Buckling, lamination parameters, tailoring, particle swarm optimization

SUMMARY

Recently developed expressions for capturing the design space of layered composites are used to measure potential design spaces of anisotropic composites. It is found that by using ply orientations with increments of 5° from -85° to 90° captures more than 97% of the possible design space.

This result suggests that exploitation of any possible tailoring scenario using layered composites made from unidirectional layers, requires only a reduced, finite set of ply orientations. The effect of using a wider set of ply orientations is considered for buckling efficiency of flat plates under compression and shear loading.

INTRODUCTION

The A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} terms are functions of the material invariants, U_1-U_5 and lamination parameters, ξ_i^j (e.g. Fukunaga [1]) as

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{22} \\ A_{12} \\ A_{66} \\ A_{16} \\ A_{26} \end{pmatrix} = h \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^A & \xi_2^A & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1^A & \xi_2^A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^A & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^A & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_3^A / 2 & \xi_4^A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^A / 2 & -\xi_4^A & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} B_{11} \\ B_{22} \\ B_{12} \\ B_{66} \\ B_{16} \\ B_{26} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{h^2}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \xi_1^B & \xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\xi_1^B & \xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^B / 2 & \xi_4^B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^B / 2 & -\xi_4^B & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{12} \\ D_{66} \\ D_{16} \\ D_{26} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{h^3}{12} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \xi_1^D & \xi_2^D & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -\xi_1^D & \xi_2^D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^D & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi_2^D & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \xi_3^D / 2 & \xi_4^D & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \xi_3^D / 2 & -\xi_4^D & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The lamination parameters may be calculated from the following integrals

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^A &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta(z), \cos 4\theta(z), \sin 2\theta(z), \sin 4\theta(z)] dz \\ \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^B &= \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta(z), \cos 4\theta(z), \sin 2\theta(z), \sin 4\theta(z)] z dz \\ \xi_{[1,2,3,4]}^D &= \frac{3}{2} \int_{-1}^1 [\cos 2\theta(z), \cos 4\theta(z), \sin 2\theta(z), \sin 4\theta(z)] z^2 dz \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where z is the through-thickness coordinate and $\theta(z)$ is the distribution function of the ply orientations through the normalised thickness co-ordinate $\bar{z} = \frac{2}{h} z$ where h is the thickness of the laminate. The material invariants, U_i , are linear functions of the ply stiffness properties, Q_{ij} , as given for example, by Jones [2],

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= \frac{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}}{8} \\ U_2 &= \frac{Q_{11} - Q_{22}}{2} \\ U_3 &= \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}}{8} \\ U_4 &= \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}}{8} \\ U_5 &= \frac{U_1 - U_4}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

It is noted that the material invariants provide useful physical insight into possible laminate response. First, it is noted that all lamination parameters, ξ_1 - ξ_{12} are zero for the quasi-isotropic modulus. Secondly, U_1 is an intrinsic measure of the quasi-isotropic Young's modulus for the material. Since Q_{22} , Q_{12} and Q_{66} are typically much smaller than Q_{11} an estimate of its value may be obtained from

$$U_1 \approx \frac{3Q_{11}}{8} \quad (4)$$

which allows the designer to obtain an approximate value of the quasi-isotropic stiffness of a laminate from knowledge of its unidirectional modulus. Furthermore, U_4/U_5 is the quasi-isotropic Poisson's ratio and U_5 is the quasi-isotropic shear modulus. It is noted that for larger

U_2 and U_3 the greater potential there is for orthotropic and anisotropic elastic tailoring as shown by the maximum range of direct and shear stiffnesses,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11}(\max) - A_{11}(\min) &= 2tU_2 \\ A_{66}(\max) - A_{66}(\min) &= 2tU_3 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

obtained by substituting $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° into A_{11} and $\theta = 45^\circ$ and 0° (or 90°) into A_{66} , in Eqn. (1), respectively. As such, U_2 may be viewed as the ability to tailor the effective Young's modulus, E_{xx} (or E_{yy}) and U_3 as the scope for tailoring the effective shear modulus, G_{xy} of a plate.

Note, only the twelve lamination parameters, defined in Eqn. (2), are necessary to model the stiffness properties of any monolithic laminated composite. The linear dependence of stiffnesses in terms of lamination parameters renders many useful structural optimisations to be convex in nature [3]. As such, optimisation studies may be relatively rapid. However, due to the trigonometrical character of lamination parameters there are constraining relationships between them which need to be known if the design space is fully characterised. The derivation of relationships between lamination parameters to provide a feasible region has been partially developed in an incremental fashion by several authors. The earliest use of lamination parameters in composite design appears to have been undertaken by Miki [4] and Miki and Sugiyama [5] who pioneered their use in optimisation studies. In doing so, he defined the feasible region between some of the lamination parameters. Specifically, he determined the feasible regions needed to describe both the in-plane or out-of-plane stiffnesses of an orthotropic laminate using two in-plane or two out-of-plane lamination parameters respectively,

$$2(\xi_1^j)^2 - 1 \leq \xi_2^j \quad (6)$$

where $j = A, D$. These feasible regions were used to provide an efficient, accurate and graphical approach to the design of laminated composites. Later, Fukunaga and Sekine [6] derived the feasible regions of the four in-plane and separately, four out-of-plane, lamination parameters,

$$2(1 + \xi_2^j)(\xi_3^j)^2 - 4\xi_1^j \xi_3^j \xi_4^j + (\xi_4^j)^2 - (\xi_2^j - 2(\xi_1^j)^2 + 1)(1 - \xi_2^j) \leq 0 \quad (7)$$

$$(\xi_1^j)^2 + (\xi_3^j)^2 \leq 1 \quad (8)$$

where $j = A, D$. For a solely out-of-plane problem, such as initial buckling, knowledge of the complete feasible region makes the optimisation process more efficient. At this time, the feasible region of the coupling lamination parameters, where ply orientations are unrestricted, had not been derived. Next, Grenestedt and Gudmundson [3] used a variational approach to implicitly determine the feasible region of orthotropic symmetric laminates. Furthermore, Grenestedt and Gudmundson derived explicit expressions between certain sets of in-plane and out-of-plane lamination parameters. For example,

$$\frac{1}{4}(\xi_i^A + 1)^3 - 1 \leq \xi_i^D \leq \frac{1}{4}(\xi_i^A - 1)^3 + 1 \quad (9)$$

where $i = 1...4$. Note, for a given value of ξ_i^A , there exists a range of values for ξ_i^D for all values except for $\xi_i^A = \pm 1$ when $\xi_i^A = \xi_i^D$. Diaconu et al [7] used the approach of Grenestedt and Gudmundson to obtain an implicit mathematical formulation of the general feasible region of all 12 lamination parameters. Also, Diaconu et al [8] derived the feasible region of lamination parameters linking the in-plane, coupling and out-of-plane lamination parameters, where the index of the parameter was the same.

$$4(\xi_i^A + 1)(\xi_i^D + 1) \geq (\xi_i^A + 1)^4 + 3(\xi_i^B)^2 \quad (10)$$

$$4(\xi_i^A - 1)(\xi_i^D - 1) \geq (\xi_i^A - 1)^4 + 3(\xi_i^B)^2 \quad (11)$$

where $i = 1...4$. It is noted that in the above studies, no restrictions were placed on potential ply orientations. Later, Diaconu and Sekine [9] derived explicitly the feasible regions of lamination parameters for $0, 90, \pm 45$ degree plies. Also, Setoodeh et al [10] developed a method to approximate the boundary of the general feasible region for lamination parameters, using the method of convex hull. Most recently, the authors developed closed form solutions [11] to describe the design space of layered composites for ply orientations which are limited to any predefined finite set, e.g. $0^\circ, 90^\circ, \pm 45^\circ$ as commonly used in the aerospace industry. By representing distinct ply orientations in terms of lamination parameters it was shown that the design space of composites can be represented in terms of three 4-dimensional spaces, each representing in-plane (A-matrix), coupling (B-matrix) and flexural (D-matrix) response. These finite, convex spaces are polygonal in nature and have nonlinear links between them. These nonlinear links represent constraining algebraic relationships between the three design spaces, where each nonlinear link is itself a function of each distinct ply orientation considered. It is noteworthy that an increasing set of ply orientations yields an increasing convex polyhedron. The polyhedron is bounded by n-dimensional hyperplanes.

The novelty of the current work is, first of all, establishing the effect of different sets of ply orientations on potential design space, before using these design spaces to observe the effect of both standard and non-standard ply orientations on buckling capacity.

LAMINATE DESIGN SPACE

Lamination parameters, due to their simple trigonometric nature, are bounded between non-dimensional values of -1 and 1. Each four dimensional space, therefore has a hyperspace volume of 2^4 which is 16. However, the actual design space is significantly lower due to the limiting constraining relationships between lamination parameters. Using the method outlined in Reference 11 it is possible to evaluate the volume of design space for different sets of allowable ply orientations. The expectancy is that as the number of possible ply orientations is increased uniformly then the volume of the design space approaches an asymptotic limit. This limit is expected to be the same volume that would be obtained if all possible continuous ply angles were used. By doing such a study and by monitoring convergence, it can be shown that the approximate volume of the feasible region, denoted (Vol_j) where $j = A, D$, for in-plane and out-of-plane lamination parameters for an unrestricted design envelope respectively, is 3.2890. As such the constraining relationships between lamination parameters significantly reduce the potential design space from 16 to 3.289.

Table 1 (Feasible region volume for in-plane and out-of-plane lamination parameters)

Set of ply orientation (in degrees)	Number of constraints	Volume of feasible region (Vol_j^*)	Relative volume (%)
[0,90,±45]	4	1.3333	41
[0,90,±45,±30,±60]	20	1.5774	48
[0,90,±45,±15,±30,±60,±75]	54	2.5981	79
5 Degree Increments between [-85, 90]	594	3.2071	97.5
2.5 Degree Increments	2484	3.2690	99.4
1 Degree Increments	15930	3.2865	99.92

It is noted that the volume of the feasible region of the in-plane lamination parameters is identical to the volume of the feasible region of out-of-plane lamination parameters for any set of ply orientations where there are no restrictions on the nature of the lay-up, e.g. the lay-up does not need to be balanced or symmetric.

By monitoring convergence, it can be shown that the approximate volume of the feasible region, denoted (Vol_B), for the four coupling lamination parameters for any possible set of ply orientations is 6.6469.

Table 2 (Feasible region volume for coupling lamination parameters)

Set of ply orientation (in degrees)	Number of constraints	Volume of feasible region (Vol_B^*)	Relative volume (%)
[0,90,±45]	8	3.3333	50
[0,90,±45,±30,±60]	88	3.7704	57
[0,90,±45,±15,±30,±60,±75]	102	5.3207	80
5 Degree Increments between [-85, 90]	1170	6.4896	97.6
2.5 Degree Increments	4932	6.6085	99.4
1 Degree Increments	31770	6.6421	99.93

It can clearly be seen from Tables 1 and 2 that as the number of distinct ply orientations increases then so does the number of constraints on the feasible region of lamination

parameters. Furthermore, from Tables 1 and 2 it is observed that the feasible region of lamination parameters can be approximated to within a 2.5% margin of the maximum obtainable volume, using a finite set of ply orientations. This feasible region consists of 5 degree increments between [-90, 90] for the ply orientations. This tolerance is obtained with 594 in-plane constraints. Interestingly, for an orthotropic symmetric laminate, $\xi_3^A, \xi_4^A, \xi_3^D, \xi_4^D = 0$ the area (since the feasible region is two dimensional) of the in-plane or out-of-plane feasible region (ξ_1^A, ξ_2^A and ξ_1^D, ξ_2^D respectively) is 2.666. The feasible region is well approximated by a set of 0,90,±30,±45,±60 degree plies which has a corresponding area of 2.5. For this particular set of plies there is a 6.2 % relative error by using such few ply orientations, which suggests for design of orthotropic laminates then only a few ply orientations is required to obtain almost any combination of stiffness values. In summary, the information regarding the volume of the feasible regions may be used to determine the number of unique ply orientations to obtain specific types of anisotropic elastic response and so could be useful for elastic tailoring purposes.

BUCKLING CONSIDERATIONS

Buckling analysis is undertaken using closed form solutions [12-13]. The plate is assumed to be flat, simply supported on all four edges and under compression or shear loads. Non-dimensionalized parameters [14] are used to calculate buckling coefficients in order to determine the critical buckling loads. The non-dimensionalized parameters are defined in terms of the out-of-plane stiffnesses,

$$\alpha = \sqrt[4]{\frac{D_{22}}{D_{11}}}, \beta = \frac{D_{12} + 2D_{66}}{\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}, \gamma = \frac{D_{16}}{\sqrt[4]{D_{11}^3D_{22}}}, \delta = \frac{D_{26}}{\sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3}} \quad (12)$$

In Ref. 26, the critical buckling stress resultant of a flexurally anisotropic plate which is simply supported on all four edges under compression loading is given by

$$N_x^{cr} = K_x \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}} \quad (13)$$

where K_x is a non-dimensional buckling coefficient given by,

$$K_x = 2(1 + \beta) - 2(3 + \beta + 2\gamma^2) \frac{(\gamma + 3\delta)^2}{(3 + \beta)^2} - 4(\delta + 2\gamma^3 - \beta\gamma) \frac{(\gamma + 3\delta)^3}{(3 + \beta)^3} \quad (14)$$

It is noted that sufficient accuracy for K_x is obtained when $|\gamma|, |\delta| < 0.4$. If $|\gamma|, |\delta| > 0.4$ an iterative procedure is used to determine the value of K_x . For further details see Ref. 17. The critical shear buckling load is calculated as [13],

$$N_{xy}^{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} K_{xy} \sqrt[4]{D_{11}D_{22}^3} \quad (15)$$

where the shear buckling coefficient is given by

$$K_{xy} = 3.42 + 2.05\beta - 0.13\beta^2 - 1.79\gamma - 6.89\delta + 0.36\beta(2\gamma + \delta) - 0.25(2\gamma + \delta)^2 \quad (16)$$

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Our objective is to determine theoretically optimal buckling loads and to assess the effect of using finite sets of ply orientations on these optimum values. So that the effect of allowable design space on buckling is clearly captured, other design considerations such as strength and damage tolerance are not considered. To determine optimal buckling loads a two-level approach is employed. At the first level, stiffness terms in Eqns (13-16) are written in terms of lamination parameters and are used to minimise the objective function ($N_x / N_{x \text{ iso}}$) or ($N_{xy} / N_{xy \text{ iso}}$) subject to lamination parameter feasible region constraints, which are calculated using the methods outlined in Reference [11]. Note the “iso” subscript refers to the quasi-isotropic laminate, i.e. stiffness terms are calculated assuming all lamination parameters equate to zero. These non-dimensionalised buckling loads clearly express the improvement in buckling capacity over the notional quasi-isotropic laminate [14]. At the second level, stacking sequences are obtained using a novel particle swarm optimisation technique [15]. In the particle swarm, the control parameters ω, c_1, c_2 were replaced by a single parameter η which is a normally distributed pseudo-randomly generated number. This provided the swarm with greater diversity and thus was able to explore the search space. In the case studies, the number of plies was fixed to 10 (20 plies symmetric) and the set of possible ply orientations was either $0, 90, \pm 45$ or $0, 90, \pm 45, \pm 30, \pm 60$. In the optimization, the swarm size was set to 20. The optimizer was deemed to converge when there had been no change in the fitness function over 50 iterations. Note, the optimization was efficient, since closed form solutions were used. Additionally, the optimisation was implemented in MATLAB. Details of the overall optimisation process are given in Reference [15].

The thickness of the plate is fixed in the optimisation to be 20 plies (10 plies symmetric) and then the non-dimensionalised buckling load is maximised. Two types of material are considered, a generic carbon/epoxy, Table 3, and an idealised material in which, E_{11} is infinitely valued, such an idealisation maximises buckling performance. Two main studies to highlight benefits of elastic tailoring are undertaken. If the plate is loaded in compression, the ratio $N_x / N_{x \text{ iso}}$ is maximised. Similarly, if the plate is in pure shear, the objective function is $N_{xy} / N_{xy \text{ iso}}$. Additionally, following common industrial practice, the laminate is evaluated for specific in-plane properties (i.e. fixed percentages of each ply orientation).

Table 3 - Material Properties for Carbon/Epoxy

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	ν_{12}	Ply thickness (mm)
Carbon Epoxy	130	7	4	1.6e-6	0.3	0.125

Compression Buckling

Optimal lay-ups are shown in Table 4 for both the idealised material and carbon/epoxy. Additionally, with no restrictions on ply orientation the optimal laminate is balanced and is $[\pm 45_5]_s$ as expected. The value of $N_x / N_{x \text{ iso}} = 4/3$ and 1.27 for the idealised material and carbon/epoxy, respectively, which confirms the results from Reference [14]. Unbalanced lay-

ups reduce buckling loads under pure compression but for the case considered the optimal unbalanced lay-up is $[\pm 45_4 / 45 / 0]_s$ with $N_x / N_{x \text{ iso}} = 1.33$ and 1.27 for the idealised material and carbon/epoxy showing that the effect of such limited unbalanced lay-ups was minimal. Note, the optimal lay-up is independent of the two material types chosen, presumably reflecting the fact that E_{11} is large (in some sense) in carbon/epoxy as well as the idealised material. Furthermore, the results in Table 4 are mostly intuitive because 45 ply angles are grouped to the outer layers with remaining ply angles grouped near the mid-plane. Such results are to be expected because D-matrix terms dominate buckling phenomenon and such placement of plies tailors second moment of area effects, of each ply angle, most favourably. Finally, it may be useful to note for design purposes that lay-ups containing up to 40% of non 45 degree ply angles may still perform well in compression buckling as shown by the small reduction in buckling capacity of 3%.

Table 4 – Buckling Performance under Compression

CASE	LAYUP	$N_x / N_{x \text{ iso}}$	
		Idealised	carbon/epoxy
10% 0, 10% 90, 80% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, 45, -45, -45, 45, 0, 90]_s$	1.33	1.27
20% 0, 10% 90, 70% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, 45, -45, -45, 90, 0, 0]_s$	1.31	1.26
30% 0, 10% 90, 60% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, 45, -45, 90, 0, 0, 0]_s$	1.29	1.24
40% 0, 10% 90, 50% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, 45, 90, 0, 0, 0, 0]_s$	1.24	1.22
10% 0, 20% 60, 70% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, 45, -45, -45, 60, 60, 0]_s$	1.33	1.27
20% 0, 20% 60, 60% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, 45, -45, 60, 60, 0, 0]_s$	1.31	1.26
30% 0, 20% 60, 50% ± 45	$[-45, 45, 45, -45, -45, 60, 60, 0, 0, 0]_s$	1.3	1.24

Shear buckling

First of all if we consider maximising shear buckling performance from the following ply angles: (0,90,45,-45), then the optimal laminates are shown in Table 5. Note, no 0° plies are present in these lay-ups and there is only a marginal difference in performance between balanced and unbalanced lay-ups.

Table 5 – Optimal Buckling Performance under Shear for Laminates containing (0,90,45,-45) Ply Angles

LAYUP	$N_{xy} / N_{xy \text{ iso}}$	
	Idealised	carbon/epoxy
Unbalanced:		
$[45, 45, 90, 45, 90, 45, 90, 45, 45, 45]_s$	1.67	1.63
Balanced:		
$[45, 45, 90, 45, 90, 90, 90, -45, -45, -45]_s$	1.64	1.6

Now consider the set of ply angles: (0,90,45,-45, 60, -60) for shear consideration. Then under positive shear loading the optimal lay-up is simply $[-60_{10}]_s$ with $N_{xy}/N_{xy\text{ iso}} = 2.09$ and is the same result for carbon/epoxy and the idealised material. If we constrain the laminate to be balanced the optimal lay-up becomes $[-60_5/60_5]_s$ with $N_{xy}/N_{xy\text{ iso}} = 1.87$ and 1.86 for the idealised material and carbon/epoxy, respectively. Note the sign of the optimal ply angle reverses under negative shear loading (for the unbalanced case).

Table 6 considers the buckling performance of (0,90,45,-45, 60, -60) ply orientations with a variety of fixed percentages of each ply orientation. Further note, that including only 20% of 60° plies may give $N_{xy}/N_{xy\text{ iso}} = 1.83$ which performs well compared with a balanced laminate containing only 60° plies ($N_{xy}/N_{xy\text{ iso}} = 1.87$).

Table 6 – Buckling Performance under Shear for Laminates containing (0,90,45,-45 and 60) Ply Angles

CASE	LAYUP	$N_{xy} / N_{xy\text{ iso}}$	
		Idealised	carbon/epoxy
10% 0, 10% 90, 80% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 45, 0, -45, -45, -45, -45] _s	1.55	1.51
20% 0, 10% 90, 70% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 45, 0, 0, -45, -45, -45] _s	1.56	1.51
30% 0, 10% 90, 70% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 45, 0, 0, 0, -45, -45] _s	1.56	1.51
40% 0, 10% 90, 50% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 45, 0, 0, 0, 0, -45] _s	1.56	1.51
10% 0, 20% 90, 70% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 90, 45, 0, -45, -45, -45] _s	1.63	1.58
10% 0, 30% 90, 60% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 90, 45, 90, 0, -45, -45] _s	1.65	1.61
10% 0, 40% 90, 50% ±45	[45, 45, 90, 45, 90, 45, 90, 90, 0, -45] _s	1.66	1.62
10% 0, 20% 60, 70% ±45	[60, 60, 45, 45, 45, 45, 0, -45, -45, -45] _s	1.81	1.77
20% 0, 20% 60, 60% ±45	[60, 60, 45, 45, 45, 45, 0, 0, -45, -45] _s	1.83	1.78
30% 0, 20% 60, 50% ±45	[60, 60, 45, 45, 45, 45, 0, 0, 0, -45] _s	1.83	1.78

CONCLUSIONS

The size of potential design space for fully anisotropic laminates is determined as a function of the number of fixed ply orientations. As such, the scope for elastic tailoring is established. It is found that by using ply orientations with increments of 5° from -85° to 90° captures more than 97% of the possible design space for anisotropic laminates. Using this knowledge of design space, optimal (and sub-optimal) lay-ups were examined for the cases of buckling under pure compression and shear. It was shown that it is possible to obtain near optimal solutions using relatively few unique fibre orientations. Furthermore, significant proportions of non-optimal ply angles could be accommodated without significantly comprising buckling capability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Both authors would like to thank Airbus and Great Western Research for sponsoring this research.

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